

Valdelia

Closing the loop in the second life furniture market

Financed through an environmental contribution as part of furniture producers' extended product responsibility, Valdelia recuperates used professional furniture and closes the loop in four ways: second hand, re-use, upcycling and material recycling.

Highlights of innovative features

- Valdelia is a non-profit environmental organization with a national collection network connecting 1,200 members including manufacturers, distributors and importers on the regional and local level.
- Around 100,000 tons of used furniture are collected annually across the whole French territory, which of 3,000 tons are reused or enter an upcycling process.
- Many of the furniture upcycling initiatives also provide local jobs including social reintegration concepts.

Valdelia's innovation department has a twofold mission:

1) to explore innovative technical + organisational solutions to develop second life in the professional furniture sector.

2) to support the sector's players in applying these solutions to their manufacturing and distribution models as well as promoting eco-design and extending the life of products.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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Valdelia
GARANTIR LA SECONDE VIE DES PRODUITS

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